

Research Article

Impacts of Terrorism on Science and Technological Development in Nigerian Education

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Abstract

Terrorism is seen as a violent product of an equal distribution of power on local, national or global levels. A nation cannot afford to treat with levity the security of its territorial integrity and of its people. Nigeria has been faced with and is still facing security challenges. This situation has made Nigerians to suffer series of economic, political and social loss of national development than gain. The paper examined science as a rational and systematic study of the environment through experimentation and observation, with a view of understanding the environment in order to manipulate and control it for the betterment of human needs. The paper sought to look at the concept terrorism, its brief history and causes in Nigeria, terrorism and national development and effect of technology on development in Nigeria. The researchers profer some suggestions toward addressing the menace of terrorism in Nigeria such as: the present government should checkmate the menace of corruption which is one of the major causes of terrorism in Nigeria; creation of more job opportunity and the security task force should rise up to their professional calling so as to prevent further loss of life.

Key words: Impacts, Terrorism, Science, Technological Development, Nigerian Education

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Introduction

Science is the rational and systematic study of the environment through experimentation and observation with a view to understanding the environment in order to manipulate and control it for the betterment of human conditions. The study of science provides both theoretical and practical knowledge about the environment, which can be used to manipulate and harness the forces and resources of nature for human development and well-being. Obamanu and Akporehwe (2012) note that these practices have scientific and technological implications that will fast-track the development of the nation.

Technology on the other hand, is the practical use of scientific knowledge and techniques to produce goods and services to meet human needs. UNESCO (2013) explains that technology uses knowledge, tools, and skills to increase human potential to solve practical problems and to modify the world. Technology gives people the capacity to control both the man-made and natural environments; create wealth; sustain socioeconomic, and natural development of the society.

Science and technology are crucial factor; for national development worldwide. Akpa (2008), stresses that both science and technology contributed immensely to the development of nations. The issue of technology is of considerable importance for economic prosperity and is needed in developing country like Nigeria. It is clear that those nations in the forefront of security and those countries that have invented enormous resources for science and technology development. Issues bordering on technological development of any nation is that of security. Every society across the globe has its peculiar problems and challenges, Nigeria is not left behind. Oyedeji (2010) laments that Nigeria still remains an underdeveloped economy principally because of the unsatisfactory status of insecurity around the nation. As a developing country, Nigeria faced share of social, political, economic and cultural problems that led to terrorism, which has in no small measure affected the wellbeing of the populace (Adebayo, 201). Every country is aspiring to reach a point of security by protecting its citizens from violence, crime, and social insecurity.

Subsequently, without the safety of citizens, all plans for development whether economic, political or social and so on will fail. Terrorism is a phenomenon eating deep into various countries across the globe in varying capacities as it affects the development

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of the nation. Any nation striving towards development must put aside crime such as violence, social insecurity and other vices that lead to terrorism for meaningful development. This paper discusses the meaning of science and technology, concept of terrorism and its brief history in Nigeria, causes of terrorism, terrorism and national development, suggestions and conclusion.

Concept of Terrorism

Scholars over the years generally have been on the disagreements as to the meaning of terrorism. Terrorism is seen as value laden and subjectively defined in line with the ideological school of the individual definition. Thus, terrorism practiced and justified by the terrorist themselves, is a tool used to achieve a particular outcome by using force, threat or violence on one segment of society with the primary aim of causing the society to be in fear and make changes in the society where they penetrated (Gerrison, 2004). Terrorists attack is a product of complex interactions between individuals, organizations and environments resulting in death and damages to properties. Terrorism is the damage done to people and the entire society where it kills, damages immediately (Farok, 2012). Nigeria is still facing such challenges now.

Brief History of Terrorism in Nigeria

Terrorism first started in Nigeria as violence in the 1980s before maturing to the present state today. This is because there were no prove to show that certain groups were behind the violence. The group became known in Kano as a result of religious violence in 1980-1993 with a leader known as Marwa Maitatsine who hailed from Northern Cameroon. The group later metamorphosed into a sect called Boko Haram (Western Education is Sin) with the leader called Muhammed Yusuf. The death of their leader led to the spread of their activities in Nigeria. The members of the sect are assumed to be from the Kanuri tribe who are concentrated in the Northeastern states of Nigeria like Bauchi, Borno and the Fulanis in Plateau State.

Furthermore, food terrorism is another form of terrorism that deals with food intake by human beings. It can be seen as the use of contaminated or poisoned food against civilians for the objectives of causing fear, illness or death and most significantly, political tension. Terrorism creates a harsh condition and providing a fertile ground for social unrest, conflict and instability to lives. In Nigeria, quite a number of people lost their lives during

the conflict and unrest in the 2001 - 2014 that could be due to political, religious, social and economic interest of certain aggrieved politicians.

Terrorism Causes in Nigeria

Many scholar including but not limited to Nigeria from various disciplines have all identified root causes of terrorism as key to understanding why most terrorism occurs. Bloom (2007) enumerates some root causes of terrorism among others as: unemployment, corruption, lack of rule of law and weak states providing hiding places for terrorists. Unemployment is a situation where there is no white collar job for the citizenry to work and earn their living. Mark (2007), sees unemployment as a situation where youths are not engaged in meaningful work and are lacking basic necessities and bring attention to their plight by engaging themselves in destructive behaviour.

Corruption is another cause of terrorism identified by Bloom which is an effort of securing wealth or position, through unlawful means for private or self-gain at the expense of others or the public. This situation makes the other masses to remain in abject poverty at the expense of those corrupt individuals. This unequal distribution means of securing wealth or power at local, national or at global levels are violent product of terrorism.

Furthermore, there are some weak states that provide hiding place for those terrorists leading to breaking of law and orders in their operation. This situation has led to the dead of thousand Nigerians, who are innocent in the menace of corruption. Peter (2013), identifies other factors to include poverty as a cause of terrorism in Nigeria which crippled the system whereby the poor become poorer and the rich become richer at the expense of the masses. This factor has made people resort to all sorts of means to meet their need whether such means are permitted by law or not. This situation is common in the Niger Delta area where oil spillage has made the people redundant, hopeless and those in abject poverty. This led to kidnapping, armed robbery, sea piracy and other vices in the area.

The second factor according to Peter is religious. He said religion is the major factor that breed terrorism in the world. He added that people hide under the context of religion and perpetuate violence as it is the easiest way to get attention of government and to weep up sentiment among their faithful. This situation is common in Nigeria particularly

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in Plateau and Kano states to mention just but a few. Other factors identified by Peter were lack of infrastructure, basic services and equality due to corruption. This situation is worst in Nigeria as only one percent of the elites controlling 80 percent of the crude oil wealth. Furthermore, ethnic identity is also considered as a factor militating against terrorism due to preferential treatment in terms of access to jobs, education, housing, drivers' permit or university admission and public services is given to individuals whose ethnicity is indigenous to the local area. That is to say if you are born in a particular state, it will be more difficult to get work in another state. If given a job it will be on contract bases and not permanent.

Besides, the above factors, others could be as a result of rise of indigenous neo elites, executive lawlessness, relative deprivation, oppression, neo-imperialist class, do or die politicking, human right violation, unjust and equitable distribution of national resources including political positions or posts, industries, investment, fund and so on. The increasing causes of terrorism are the same with factors that threaten security everywhere across the earth globe. This was affirmed by Ajakaiye (2002:8) and Jega (2007:199), but poverty appears to be the greatest underlying threats to security in Nigeria. They further opined that a combination of widening gap in income inequality worsening unemployment situation and perception of group discrimination and marginalization based on ethnic religious and communal differences (Nwachukwu, 2011:76).

Terrorism and National Development

National development is a gradual growth of something so that it becomes more advanced, or a stage that is likely to affect what happens in a continuing situation. Jacob and Dorah (2014) see national development as a process of growth or advancement of a nation until its get to a point of competitiveness with the world leading economy, the main aim of any national development policy is to improve the quality of life of citizens and especially to conserve the vitality and diversity of mankind. This also guides man efforts at ensuring life in harmony with his fellow men and with nature and creating impact on the socio-economic development of the society. Thus, national development refers to the ability of a nation to improve the lives of its citizens. Such nation has good means of transportation, good health care, communication means, good means of agriculture, electricity, accommodation, defense, industrial productivity, education and recreational facilities for its citizenry.

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A nation can only enjoy the above facilities under a stable and peaceful government where the national resource of that country is equitably distributed at all levels of government without bias. A country where corruption unemployment, unstable government, violent and what have you are the order of the day, that country will remain under develop forever. Terrorism is seen as violent product of an unequal distribution of power on local, national, or global levels. A nation cannot afford to treat with levity the security of its territorial integrity and of its people. Infact every aspect of human endeavors, be it health, food, environmental, economy, political, social and physiological, stands to be greatly affected by the state of security or insecurity of that nation. Nigeria has been faced and is still facing the challenging security issues. This situation has made Nigerians to suffer series of economic, political and social loss of national development than gain. Dalyop (2013) says a nation under this terror is faced with the following implications. Concerning the economic implications, the rural dwellers who engage in small scale agriculture and large scale farming as a means of livelihood, feeding of the urban areas and supply of industries with raw materials is no more due to attacks and killing and escaped of the surviving ones. The danger is that there would be food shortage in the nearest future in such areas. More so, that the attacks involves cutting down of food crops on the farm and burning of ripped store ones, cattle rustling and theft in attack areas like Barakin Ladi, Riyom, Bokkos and part of Mangu Local Government from 2013 - 2015 suffered this terror attacked.

The facilities for agriculture provided by science and technology such as tractors, plough machines, harvesters, agro-chemicals like herbicides and a lot of others will be redundant as their patronage will not be there to improve food production due to dead and their escaped for safety.

The social gathering for activities such as cultural dances, folktale, visitation, market and others are no longer tenable due to fear of attacks in the rural areas. The insecurity in Nigeria has degenerated to a level such that people are attacked while mourning or performing funeral rites of their loved one. The rural people are dislodged from their ancestral land and homes and forced to become refugees in camps in their homeland. There is an upsurge in social vices such as human right abuses, children education, prostitution, rape; theft and armed robbery are on increase and sexual harassment. These factors are against the growth, development such as access to education, health care, defense, economic and social development and corporate existence of any nation.

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The production of drugs and vaccines for human health to help increase life span on earth will not be used effectively and the result is death. The provision of electricity for lightening the house, cooking food, powering engines and other machines will no longer be there for use due to fear and destructions to life by the attackers.

On the part of political implications a lot of victims attacked by terrorists had their voters card burned in their houses or lost them while running for their safety. Those displaced may not be secured to go back and vote. Besides, there would be restrictions in terms of political campaigns and electioneering due to the unequal nature of the settlement. This situation may lead to unpopular candidates against the majority will be emerged.

Effects of Technology on Development in Nigeria

A country where there is absence of peace, suffer economically, socially and politically leaving that country underdeveloped. Adejoh and Ekele (2014:14), lament that, the greatest threats to peace today is science and technology who produces nuclear, biological and atomic bombs that are dangerous to human life when used by the enemies. Technology has negative effect on moral and ethical issues as children are exposed to things that they are not supposed to in the mass media and internet as browsing of pornography on the net thereby corrupting their minds at tender age. Influence of Africans cultural alienation. In Africa we have a culture but today, technology has affected it due to mass media, internet and so on making us to alienate from these cultural heritage.

The rate of poverty has also increased as a result of science and technology. This is because many commodities, goods and services are beyond the teaching of common man. As a result of industrial activities, the lands are being polluted and are no longer fit for agricultural activities. Job that human beings engage in for a living have been taken over by the machines for instance farms, ATM, taking over the jobs of cashiers in bank and robots in factories also taking over human jobs leaving many of the masses unemployed.

Furthermore, the world is becoming over populated due to science and technology, as people get treated of different diseases with drugs, vaccines and as a result birth rate is more than death rate. This is making the resources to be scarce and there is competition for available resources. Technology generally though has a number of negative effects,

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the important outweighed it if justice and equity is embraced in Nigeria as order of the day.

Suggestions

In view of the rampant cases of terrorism in Nigeria, the present government should check all forms of corruptions at all levels with an appropriate punishment made by the law of the country.

The creation of more jobs opportunities for Nigerian as said by the present government during the 2014 campaign should be considered paramount to avoid idleness among the masses.

The special task force must rise up to its responsibility and professional calling to salvage its already bad image and prevent further loss of life of the rural dwellers and communities in Nigeria.

The people that are the elites, most mobilize both human and material equipment to defend themselves on the one hand, and to serve as a deterrent on the other hand. The rural dwellers must revert to their pre-colonial form of security and self-defense, since the special task force and other security agencies are not enough to safe-guard their lives and properties.

Conclusion

Having looked at the conceptual definitions of science and technology, terrorism, its advert in Nigeria and effect on technology development, the paper suggested that corruption and bad governance must be addressed in order to have a society devoid of terrorism and other forms of violence in Nigeria-studies from other parts of the country revealed that terrorism does not happen in a vacuum, there must be a cause and until the cause is addressed, loss of lives and property which is against any development may not end. Good governance must be permitted to survive in Nigeria if there must be democratic stability.

The ideas of the terrorists (Boko Haram) have spread as wild fire in parts because of many socioeconomic grievances that have produced a perceived marginalization and insecurity

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among northern Muslim communities. In addition, its animosity toward the Nigerian government is shared broadly among Nigerians, regardless of faith but particularly in the north and prominently among Muslim communities. If the present government does not address it, the existence of terrorism in Nigeria will continue to threaten the unity, peace and development of Nigeria.

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